

A performance-based approach for coupling cradle-to-use LCA with operational energy simulation for Calcium Silicate and Clay Bricks in masonry buildings

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Abstract

A performance-based approach for assessing the environmental impact of masonry buildings is proposed. This new method combines Life Cycle Assessment and operational energy (OE) simulations to compare the cradle-to-use environmental performance of a reference building composed of single core masonry walls made of Calcium Silicate Bricks (CSB) and Clay Bricks in Germany over a period of 50 years. To achieve this, a detailed process-based life cycle inventory and a methodology that combines material embodied footprints with operational energy simulations is developed, while also considering the vertical limit state for loading the walls. The study also considers the impact of future electricity mixes, the efficiency of heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems and the effect of lime-based construction materials carbonation on the optimal insulation thickness for a reference building. Results show that the OE consumption is the dominant phase in the overall environmental performance of current masonry buildings. Moreover, the balance between the material embodied footprint (MEF) and the OE at use phase, strongly depends on the impact category under study. If fully renewable-based electricity supply and highly efficient heat pumps are implemented, the role of MEF plays a decisive role, particularly in terms of climate change and resource availability damage areas. Moreover, the role of carbonation in CSB may contribute to up to 20% of carbon footprint reduction at a building scale.

Key words: LCA, Operational Energy, Calcium Silicate Brick, Clay Brick, Carbonation.

Abbreviations

<i>Aquatic Acidification Potential</i>	AAP	<i>Life Cycle Impact Assessment</i>	LCIA
<i>Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential</i>	AETP	<i>Life Cycle Inventory</i>	LCI
<i>Aquatic Eutrophication Potential</i>	AEP	<i>Material Embodied Footprint</i>	MEF
<i>Calcium Silicate Brick</i>	CSB	<i>Mineral Extraction</i>	ME
<i>Carcinogens Potential</i>	CP	<i>Mortar Renders & Plasters</i>	MRP
<i>Characterisation Factor</i>	CF	<i>Non-carcinogens Potential</i>	NCP
<i>Clay Brick</i>	CB	<i>Non-renewable Energy</i>	NRE
<i>Climate Change</i>	CC	<i>Operational Energy</i>	OE
<i>Ecosystems Quality</i>	EQ	<i>Ozone Layer Depletion Potential</i>	ODP
<i>Environmental Product Declaration</i>	EPD	<i>Photochemical Oxidation Potential</i>	POCP

Abbreviations - continued

<i>Functional Unit</i>	FU	<i>Resource Availability</i>	RA
<i>Global Warming Potential</i>	GWP	<i>Respiratory Inorganics</i>	RI
<i>Greenhouse Gas</i>	GHG	<i>Seasonal Coefficient of Performance</i>	SCOP
<i>Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning</i>	HVAC	<i>Single Score</i>	SS
<i>Human Health</i>	HH	<i>Social Life Cycle Assessment</i>	SLCA
<i>Impact Category</i>	IC	<i>Sustainable Building Lime applications via Circular Economy and Biomimetic Approaches</i>	SUBLime
<i>Ionizing Radiation</i>	IR	<i>Terrestrial Acidification Potential</i>	TAP
<i>Land Occupation</i>	LO	<i>Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential</i>	TETP
<i>Life Cycle Assessment</i>	LCA	<i>United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change</i>	UNFCCC

29

30 **1 Introduction**

31 The global Green-House-Gas (GHG) emissions grew 0.9% in 2022 [1], and with this heavily jeopardizing the
32 Paris Agreement's target on keeping the global temperature increase below 1.5 °C [2]. The manufacturing,
33 construction, and energy use in buildings contributed for nearly 30% of these emissions [3]. While the
34 cement industry is often cited for its large share of the global anthropogenic GHG emissions, lime-based
35 construction materials also produce significant amounts of CO₂ emissions due to a similar kind of
36 calcination process [4]. Moreover, the European Lime Association (EuLA) disclosed a growing trend in CaO
37 production in the past years, especially emphasizing the construction materials sector, which represents
38 11.6% of the European lime market share [5]. Along with this, Life cycle assessment (LCA), as defined by
39 ISO 14040/44 [6], is commonly used as a methodology to evaluate a building's environmental footprint
40 from a holistic point of view, while considering the various life cycle stages as stated in the European
41 Standard EN-15804 [7]. A recent study by Bahramian [8] showed that on average, the operational energy
42 (OE) requirement of a building is the predominant phase that represents typically over 60% of the total
43 life cycle energy, while the embodied energy of materials is around 40%. However, the variability of the
44 OE ratio relative to the total life cycle energy ranges from 25% to 95%, depending on the building's lifetime.
45 As about 60% of the building sector's energy use is delivered by fossil fuels [9], further investigation is
46 needed to understand its environmental consequences.

47 Many studies focus on the LCA of masonry systems at a material level while lacking a clear coupling with
48 a model that provides the analyses of the energy performance during use phase. While some studies
49 compare materials as such, they often disregard a consideration of the building-scale performance [10]–
50 [13]. Conversely, studies that consider operational energy (OE) simulation often lack sufficient detail in life
51 cycle inventory (LCI) developments [14], when using generic environmental datasets. Some studies use
52 optimization methods related to energy retrofitting and LCA, LCC (Life Cycle Costing), and SLCA (Social Life
53 Cycle Assessment) [15], but lack a detailed inclusion of a process-based LCI connected to the
54 environmental performance analysis [16].

55 **1.1 Masonry buildings LCA**

56 Specific research related to clay bricks (CBs) LCA was published by many authors. For instance, De Souza
57 [10] conducted a comparative LCA of exterior walls made from ceramic bricks, concrete bricks and cast-in-
58 place reinforced concrete in Brazil. In this study, the environmental impact of manufacturing and
59 assembling the different solutions, as well as the end of life (EoL) phase were analysed. Muñoz et al. [11]

60 performed an LCA to analyse the environmental benefits of the inclusion of Waelz slag into fired bricks,
61 with particular attention given to raw material extraction, manufacturing process and EoL treatment.
62 Similarly, Muneron et al. [12] compared the environmental performance of ceramic bricks and concrete
63 blocks in vertical systems using a cradle-to-grave LCA approach. Results highlighted the contribution of
64 fossil fuels during firing of ceramic bricks, without showing a connection with the share of various energy
65 sources needed during operation of the building. In fact, none of the before mentioned studies considered
66 the thermal or mechanical performance of these materials and its relation with the OE requirement.
67 Moreover, Landi [13] recently published an LCA of a smart clay brick monitoring system for masonry
68 buildings, including a comprehensive literature review on environmental information related to clay bricks
69 manufacturing and detailed information on the cradle-to-gate LCI. However, no performance in terms of
70 OE requirement was published, and conclusions were drawn with emphasis on comparing different
71 solutions at a material level.

72 Many studies that focus on design optimization, tend to rely on generic environmental datasets such as
73 Ecoinvent and Gabi, lacking of the necessary level of detail in their LCI. For instance, Antipova et al. [15]
74 developed a mathematical approach for optimizing an LCA of building retrofitting, including the economic
75 performance of the solution through total cost calculation. However, in this study the LCI information
76 needed for evaluating the environmental performance was disregarded. Instead, the environmental
77 impact of different energy sources (natural gas and electricity) was employed directly. Toosi et al. [16]
78 proposed a methodology for life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) of building retrofitting, which
79 included LCC and SLCA. Although the study conducted a comprehensive literature review on optimization
80 methods, energy retrofit, LCA, LCC and SLCA, a detailed process-based LCI in the environmental
81 performance analysis was disregarded. Rather, generic information on direct mid-point impact categories
82 was calculated based on the Ecoinvent database. Finally, the study highlighted the fact that reducing
83 energy consumption in the operational phase may result in an environmental load-shift towards other life
84 cycle phases.

85 **1.2 Coupled LCA and OE**

86 To couple the material embodied footprint (MEF) with the OE demand of a building, it is necessary to
87 define basic design parameters such as building geometry, location, construction system, heating
88 ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) system, among others. Since a building's energy saving potential
89 is heavily influenced by its envelope components and therefore by MEF, a non-linear, iterative procedure
90 of analysing the final environmental impact using LCA methodology is required. In a study by Landuyt et
91 al. [14], a balance between the material-related environmental impact and OE requirement was found for
92 a specific case study in Belgium. The study also examined the optimal insulation thickness of a
93 prefabricated house called *TheMobble*, as well as its relationship with design parameters such as HVAC
94 system efficiency and user comfort, using a single score indicator. However, like the aforementioned
95 studies, a clear link between the material manufacturing process and the end-point and mid-point impact
96 indicators was ignored.

97 Combining a detailed process-based LCI with the OE requirements during the use phase offers numerous
98 benefits for various stakeholders. For manufacturers, it provides a comprehensive understanding of the
99 impact of their products at final use stage, enabling them to identify areas for improvement and
100 optimization opportunities. For designers, it offers the ability to incorporate holistic environmental
101 indicators into the early stages of design. Additionally, for policy makers, it provides an in-depth
102 understanding through simulations of the interplay of all the parameters involved in the production and

103 use of construction materials, such as the use of different energy sources. This can support the
104 development of more sustainable construction policies.

105 The aim of this paper is to bridge the gap between the current knowledge of LCA at materials
106 manufacturing level and their lifecycle performance, according to i) proposing a methodology to calculate
107 the LCA at a building level, which incorporates both the material manufacturing and the OE requirements
108 in an integrated manner from the cradle-to-use phases, ii) providing a detailed and transparent process-
109 based LCI for the production of two building materials, namely calcium silicate brick (CSB) and CB, to
110 determine their environmental performance, and finally, iii) determining the optimal combination of
111 materials to produce the lowest environmental impact and conduct a parametric study of the HVAC system
112 efficiency, as well as the electricity mix used, with respect to the optimal insulation thickness while
113 considering future trends in energy use and technological advancements.

114 **2 Methodology**

115 A coupled process-based LCA and OE simulation model was developed for assessing the environmental
116 performance of masonry buildings. The main novelty of this approach is the combination of a detailed LCI
117 along with the performance of the building materials to analyse the cradle-to-use environmental
118 performance of multiple solutions in different impact categories. The case of CSB and CB, along with lime-
119 based Mortar, Render and Plaster (MRP) was investigated for Frankfurt, in Germany. Furthermore, a
120 detailed process-based LCI was developed and disclosed for the two types of bricks. For this case study,
121 the MOD 910 building from ASHRAE (American Society of Heating Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning
122 Engineers) Standard was employed, while analysing the OE requirement for 50 years of use. The effect of
123 the current and forecasted electricity mix, the HVAC efficiency and carbonation potential of the materials
124 was studied as well.

125 **2.1 Goal of the study**

126 A methodology is developed that enables an easy comparison of the environmental impact of multiple
127 masonry construction unit combinations. The methodology couples the various manufacturing phases and
128 related impacts of each construction material with the expected building-scale energy performance. The
129 mechanical performance of materials is taken into account by adjusting the quantity of material required
130 to meet the vertical loading limit state. This approach, previously introduced by Dobbelaere et al. [17] for
131 concrete structures, aims to ensure a fair comparison among different materials. As demonstrate by
132 Simone Souza [18], the choice of FU can introduce bias in building-LCA results. In fact, Bahramian et al [8]
133 analysed the FU used in different studies regarding the LCA of buildings, showing that they may vary
134 considerably. In this study, the FU is set to the unit of gross floor area. This means, that the total amount
135 of material needed for each scenario and the total OE requirement is divided by the buildings' gross floor
136 area. Since the goal of the analysis is to compare different wall solutions, neither the roof nor the floor is
137 accounted for in the LCA, although they are considered in the OE requirement simulation.

138 In the end, this methodology, along with the LCI, is applied to determine the most environmentally friendly
139 solution for the construction of masonry walls made with CSB and CB for the particular case study in
140 Frankfurt. The analysis considers 12 wall combinations, composed with a render, an insulation, a brick and
141 a plaster layer for a standard 1- story building over 50 years. Moreover, for each combination, an iterative
142 procedure for calculating the environmental performance is conducted by means of an LCA, along with
143 the energy simulation, while the thickness of the insulation material changed from 0 cm to 40 cm. The

144 optimal insulation thickness is calculated by finding the minimum environmental impact in each category.
 145 The study also provides the backgrounds of the Matlab modelling following the ISO14040/44 [6] LCA
 146 methodology.

147 2.2 Coupling methodology

148 As shown in **Figure 1**, four main steps are followed in the approach for the coupling methodology. First, all
 149 background environmental data needed for the LCI definition and calculation is imported from Ecoinvent
 150 v3.8 [19] into Matlab. All different manufacturing processes related to production of construction
 151 materials are modelled and parametrized as functions. This allows each product to be used either directly
 152 in the functional unit calculation or to be requested by other processes during manufacturing of a new
 153 material. To account for regional representativeness, a country-specific electricity mix and an industry-
 154 specific fuel mix is modelled and presented in Table A-1 of the supplementary material. Once all processes
 155 are defined based on their reference amount (e.g. 1 kg of CSB), links are established between upstream
 156 and downstream related processes. For example, the lime manufacturing function is linked to the CSB
 157 production, since it is one of the input materials. Secondly, the inventory definition at both, building and
 158 material scale has to be conducted. For this, basic material input data is taken from an own made
 159 construction material database (CM-DB) build from different sources like Environmental Product
 160 Declarations (EPDs), research papers and manufacturer catalogues. Based on the building's main
 161 properties, different wall compositions are defined and compared through the differences in mechanical
 162 properties of the materials. In this study, the vertical loading limit state of the wall is calculated following
 163 the European Standard EN1996-1-1 [20] and an equivalent depth capable of withstanding a similar vertical
 164 load is determined for each wall. A Matlab algorithm is developed to solve the LCI by following the matrix
 165 structure defined by Heijungs et. al [21]. The production of each material works as an individual function,
 166 where the technology matrix A is parametrized and solved. Thirdly, all possible combinations are
 167 normalized to the system FU of 1 m² of the building's gross area. The OE requirement of the reference
 168 building is obtained from the open source EnergyPlus software [22] and an OE profile is established for
 169 each wall combination. Finally, the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), following IMPACT 2002+
 170 methodology, is implemented in Matlab in order to automatically calculate all different scenario results.
 171 Midpoint, endpoint and single score indicators are calculated and compared by focussing on the relative
 172 contribution of the different processes on the overall score.

173

174

Figure 1: Four step coupling methodology scheme

175 **2.2.1 Non-Linear Life Cycle Assessment calculation**

176 It is common to build up an LCI normalized to the system's functional unit, allowing to easily scale it while
177 considering a new vector of demand. Nevertheless, this requires that all the flows in the system are linearly
178 correlated. However, this is uncommonly the rule in engineering practice. In reality, non-linearities arise at
179 almost every step of the LCA analysis. For instance, for the manufacturing phase, Eden et al. showed that
180 while the mean primary energy requirement for the manufacturing of 1 ton of Calcium Silicate Brick in
181 Germany in 2010 was 120 kWh, this value could vary non-linearly between 80 kWh and 140 kWh
182 depending on the raw materials temperature before entering the autoclave [23]. Similarly, the OE
183 requirement of a building exhibits a non-linear dependency on materials properties such as thickness,
184 thermal conductivity, heat capacity, and other relevant parameters. As discussed by Hollberg [24],
185 decisions made in the early stages of the design process have the greatest influence on the operational
186 and embodied environmental impacts, but the information available is rather scarce and uncertain. For
187 this reason, it is of great importance to develop LCA-models that can overcome this limitation and be
188 flexible enough to simulate non-linearities in the assessment. In this research, non-linear behaviour linked
189 to the operational energy requirement are considered, while the ones arising from the manufacturing
190 phase are disregarded.

191 **2.3 General Matlab structure for solving LCA**

192 The mathematical approach followed in this paper for solving LCA systems is based on a set of linear
193 equations that were inverted following the matrix inversion method which was firstly implemented by
194 Heijungs and Suh in 2002 [25]. They introduced the concept of technology matrix **A**, intervention matrix
195 **B**, demand vector **f** and scaling vector **s**. The inventory system can be written as provided in Equation 1.
196 Inverting the matrix **A** leads immediately to the solution of the inventory problem. Once the scaling vector
197 is found, it is possible to calculate the inventory vector **g**, by scaling the environmental flows in **B**, and
198 then to calculate the related impacts according to Equation 2 & 3, where **h** is the impact category vector
199 and **C** represents the matrix of characterization factors (CFs), that depend on the selected impact method.

$$200 \quad \mathbf{A} \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{f} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{f} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{s} \quad \mathbf{h} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{g} \quad \text{Equation 2 \& 3}$$

201 **2.3.1 Life cycle inventory solution**

202 Regarding the LCI solution, three main steps were followed, schematized in **Figure 2**. First, a technology
203 matrix **A_i** comprising all relevant processes listed in the inventory table for manufacturing each individual
204 material **i** is defined. It should be noted that hollow processes were created whenever necessary to achieve
205 a square matrix for a unique solution when inverting this matrix. Secondly, the corresponding demand
206 vector **f_i** for each material is calculated to fulfil the system's FU. During this step, a list of commercially
207 available bricks is used to analyse multiple solutions that adapt to the market reality. The brick's
208 compressive strength **f_b** is taken from each product's technical sheet. The amount of bricks and mortar
209 needed is calculated based on the listed geometry and the joint width and height. Once the total surface
210 of bricks and mortar is known for 1 m² of wall, an equivalent depth is determined based on structural
211 performance, as described before. Equation 4 is used to calculate the equivalent thickness **w_{eq}**, where **f_k**

212 is the characteristic compressive strength of the masonry, calculated following the European Standard
 213 EN1996-1-1 [20] considering the corresponding expression related to the brick and mortar type. In
 214 Equation 4, w_{max} denotes the thickness of the wall with the highest compressive strength value f_{kmax} .

$$w_{eq} = w_{max} * \frac{f_{kmax}}{f_k} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

215 This generalized method allows to automatically compute multiple combinations based on a material
 216 database. Furthermore, different compositions like binder proportions can be studied for a reference
 217 mortar.

218 Thirdly, the operational energy requirement is simulated for the different wall profiles, by introducing the
 219 building design parameters and the material's thermal properties into EnergyPlus software. It should be
 220 noted that the energy requirement input, here as electricity due to the use of a heat pump, should be
 221 selected by considering the type of fuel and efficiency of the system used to deliver the energy. A
 222 technology and intervention matrix A_{ope} & B_{ope} are defined for this process.

223 For each combination under study, once the reference amount f_i has been calculated, the contribution of
 224 each process, i.e. the scaling vector s_i , has to be determined. This includes the corresponding
 225 environmental flows g_i . A final inventory vector g can be calculated for each wall combination $Wall_j$.

226
 227 **Figure 2:** Information flow of the LCI

228 2.3.2 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

229 The environmental impact analysis was conducted across fifteen mid-point categories, four end-point
 230 categories and a single score indicator, following the IMPACT 2002+ method [26]. It should be emphasised,
 231 that the proposed methodology is applicable to any impact method. **Table 1** shows the different mid-point
 232 impact categories considered, along with the used conversion factors to calculate the end-point indicators.
 233 These are then multiplied by the normalization factors shown below and summed to express the single
 234 score point. The environmental impact is calculated for each wall combination and the information about
 235 the contribution of each process is stored. Results are then plotted as a function of the variable insulation
 236 and the different impact categories. By calculating the minimum environmental impact value, it is possible
 237 to find most environmentally friendly combination along with the relative contribution of each process to
 238 the overall score.

239 **Table 1:** Mid-point and End-point impact categories & conversion and normalization factors

Impact Category	Reference Unit	Reference Name	Conversion Factors
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Mid-point			HH	EQ	RA	CC
Aquatic acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	AAP	-	-	-	-
Aquatic ecotoxicity	kg TEG water	AETP	-	8.86E-05	-	-
Aquatic eutrophication	kg PO ₄ P-lim	AEP	-	-	-	-
Carcinogens	kg C ₂ H ₃ Cl eq	CP	2.80E-05	-	-	-
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	GWP	-	-	-	1.00E+00
Ionizing radiation	Bq C-14 eq	IR	2.10E-10	-	-	-
Land occupation	m ² org.arable	LO	-	1.09E+00	-	-
Mineral extraction	MJ surplus	ME	-	-	1.00E+00	-
Non-carcinogens	kg C ₂ H ₃ Cl eq	NCP	2.80E-04	-	-	-
Non-renewable energy	MJ primary	NRE	-	-	1.00E+00	-
Ozone layer depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	ODP	1.05E-03	-	-	-
Respiratory inorganics	kg PM _{2.5} eq	RI	7.00E-04	-	-	-
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq	POCP	2.13E-06	-	-	-
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	TAP	-	1.04E+00	-	-
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg TEG soil	TETP	-	8.86E-05	-	-
End-point						
Human Health	DALY	HH				
Ecosystems Quality	PDF m ² year	EQ				
Resources Availability	MJ	RA				
Climate Change	kg CO ₂ eq	CC				
				Normalization Factors		
Single Score	persons year	SS	7.10E-03	1.38E+04	1.16E+04	1.52E+05

240

241 **2.4 Life Cycle Inventory development**

242 The LCI phase as part of an LCA links all unit processes needed for manufacturing the product under study
243 [27]. This is often the most time-consuming and critical aspect of an LCA, as the results heavily rely on the
244 feasibility of the input variables. Although the ISO 14040/44 standard recommends using primary data,
245 this is not always available from research reports due to confidentiality constrains. The present study,
246 however, was conducted as part of the European SUBLime project [28], where 11 industries and 6
247 academic institutions collaborate on examining sustainable lime-based applications. The study also
248 benefited from close collaboration with the German Calcium-Silicate Brick Association [29], which allowed
249 for the gathering and validation of inventory data used in the analysis. The system boundary considered
250 in this study is illustrated in **Figure 3**.

251 In this paper, three types of CSB and CB and two types of mortar, i.e. normal joint mortar and thin joint
252 mortar, are considered, giving a total of 12 wall combinations. Furthermore, the insulation layer composed
253 by mineral wool, is modelled as variable ranging from 0 cm to 40 cm every 1 cm. **Table 2** shows all the
254 material properties considered, including the thermal conductivity λ and the density ρ . Regarding the
255 mortar mixes, it is assumed that for both the thin layer mortar and the joint normal mortar, the mean
256 compressive strength f_m is 12 N/mm². Both mix designs were taken from published EPDs [30]. For the first
257 one, 1% and 0.1% of plasticizer and air entrainer was employed relative to the binder content, respectively.
258 For the latter, these amounts were set to 0.5% and 0.0% respectively. No additives were included for the
259 plaster and the render mix design. Each production process of each material was treated as an individual
260 function and the electricity and fuel mixes were defined as separate functions to enable flexible regional
261 and industry-specific simulations.

Figure 3: System boundary

Table 2: Material properties

Bricks properties

Name	Type	Length (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Height (mm)	f_b (N/mm ²)	λ (W/m.K)	ρ (kg/m ³)
CSB-1400	CSB	248	175	248	12	0.7	1400
CSB-1800	CSB	248	175	248	12	0.99	1800
CSB-2000	CSB	248	175	248	20	1.1	2000
CB-600	CB	248	175	244	6	0.09	650
CB-600b	CB	248	365	244	6	0.09	650
CB-1200	CB	248	365	244	12	0.12	900

Mortar Render & Plasters mix and properties

Type	H. Lime (kg)	CEM I (kg)	Sand (kg)	Plasticizer (kg)	Air entrainer (kg)	f_m (N/mm ²)	λ (W/m.K)
Joint Thin	0	350	611.5	35	3.5	12	-
Joint Normal	30	310	642	18	0	12	-
Render	225	150	625	0	0	-	0.51
Plaster	300	0	700	0	0	-	0.51

Insulation properties

Type	Thickness (mm)	λ (W/m.K)	ρ (kg/m ³)	LCI dataset
Mineral Wool	Variable [0:10:400]	0.035	70	Ecoinvent V3.8 "stone wool production packed, APOS S-RoW"

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267 **Table 3** shows the total number of wall combinations with regards to the quantity of materials. Both the
268 amounts of brick and mortar are calculated with the equivalent thickness method described before

269 (Equation 4). The render and plaster thickness are set constant to 20 mm for all wall designs. The amount
 270 of insulation is not specified, as it changes with the variation of its thickness.

271 **Table 3: Wall combinations & amount of materials used per FU.**

Wall		Brick			Mortar		Render Plaster
Name	Type	f_k (N/mm ²)	t_{eq} (mm)	Amount (kg/m ²)	Type	Amount (kg/m ²)	Amount (kg/m ²)
CSB-1.4 _T	CSB-1400	6.61	270.2	497.2	Joint Thin	4.4	40.6 40.6
CSB-1.4 _N	CSB-1400	6.60	270.7	443.7	Joint Normal	65.9	40.6 40.6
CSB-1.8 _T	CSB-1800	6.61	270.2	639.2	Joint Thin	4.4	40.6 40.6
CSB-1.8 _N	CSB-1800	6.60	270.7	570.4	Joint Normal	65.9	40.6 40.6
CSB-2.0 _T	CSB-2000	10.21	175.0	460.0	Joint Thin	2.8	40.6 40.6
CSB-2.0 _N	CSB-2000	9.44	189.3	443.3	Joint Normal	46.1	40.6 40.6
CB-0.6 _T	CB-600	3.44	519.4	443.8	Joint Thin	8.4	40.6 40.6
CB-0.6 _N	CB-600	4.06	439.7	334.6	Joint Normal	107	40.6 40.6
CB-0.6b _T	CB-600b	3.44	519.4	443.8	Joint Thin	8.4	40.6 40.6
CB-0.6b _N	CB-600b	4.06	439.7	334.6	Joint Normal	107	40.6 40.6
CB-1.2 _T	CB-1200	6.20	288.2	340.9	Joint Thin	4.7	40.6 40.6
CB1.2 _N	CB-1200	6.60	270.7	285.2	Joint Normal	65.9	40.6 40.6

272
 273 The manufacturing of each construction material was considered by simulating the process flows of the
 274 production plants shown in **Figure 3**. Additionally, direct processes for the cement, additives and mineral
 275 wool were used from the Ecoinvent v3.8 database. For cement, a CEM type I was modelled by the process
 276 “*cement production Portland, APOS-S, Europe without Switzerland*”. Regarding the additives shown in
 277 **Table 2**, the processes “*carboxymethyl cellulose production, powder | APOS, S – RoW*” and “*alkylbenzene*
 278 *sulfonate, linear, petrochemical | APOS, S – RoW*” were selected as plasticizer and air entraining agent
 279 respectively. This was done, since no direct dataset was found and, according to the authors, these two
 280 alternatives can be considered as a most feasible representative option, which is based on literature [31].
 281 The mineral wool production was simulated by the process “*stone wool production packed, APOS-S RoW*”.

282 **2.4.1 Lime Manufacturing**

283 Lime has been used as a construction material for many centuries [32]. Some authors date back its use to
 284 10,000 BCE [33]. In recent years, interest in this material has gained renewed attention because of its
 285 carbonation potential during its service life, and with this, its possible use in carbon sequestration
 286 applications, which will be discussed later. The approach introduced by the authors in [4] will also be
 287 followed in this work. Based on the conservation of mass principle and the stoichiometry of reactions,
 288 each unit process comprising a theoretical lime production plant is balanced. Detailed information of the
 289 considered inventory can be found in the corresponding article [4].

290 **2.4.2 Calcium silicate brick manufacturing**

291 Since its patenting in 1886 in UK, CSB they became a major building material in Europe, especially in
 292 Germany, The Netherlands, UK and Russia [34]. Today, CSB are the second most used type of bricks in
 293 Germany, making up almost one third (30%) of Germany’s brick industry market. They represented a 406.5
 294 Mio EUR industry in 2020. The rest of the market is divided between ceramic bricks (47% share, 636.7 m

295 EUR), autoclaved aerated concrete blocks (20% share, 267.7 m EUR) and lightweight concrete blocks (4%
296 share, 51.1 m EUR) [35].

297 The manufacturing process of CSB is composed by 4 main stages, as shown in **Figure 3**. First, the raw
298 materials, namely lime (CaO) and sand, are transported and stored into silos. It was assumed that the sand
299 is extracted directly near the plant and therefore only transportation by conveyor belt is considered. The
300 lime transport distance was assumed to be 95 km, since it can range between 10 km and 200 km [36].

301 Next, each material is weighted and placed in the mixer. The amount of required water depends on the
302 sand humidity (usually in the range of 4 to 6%). A typical composition is made of 0.07 tonne CaO per ton
303 of CSB and around 0.93 tonne sand per ton CSB [37], although fillers may also be included. After an
304 intensive mixing process, the sand-lime-water mix is stored in a reaction vessel for about 1 hour where the
305 complete hydration reaction of the lime takes place. An incomplete reaction could lead into undesired
306 expansions during the autoclaving process and the associated risk of cracking [38]. Different size
307 configurations are defined in DIN 20000-402, although an increasing number of manufacturers are
308 producing customizable blocks, meaning they sized them to perfectly fit within the buildings design and
309 therefore minimize the waste during construction. Most energy intensive process in the manufacturing of
310 calcium silicate bricks is the autoclaving process. A recent report performed by the German Calcium Silicate
311 Brick Association [29] showing different strategies to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, exhibits that
312 around 87% of the total energy for CSB manufacturing is required for the water vapour production [39].
313 During autoclaving, the relative weak physical bond between the component elements (CaO, SiO₂ and H₂O)
314 is transformed, under pressurized steam, at around 180 – 200 °C and 12 – 18 bar for 4 to 12 hours, into
315 strong chemically bond calcium silicate hydrates (CSH) phases [37], [40]–[43].

316 **2.4.3 Clay brick manufacturing**

317 Although CBs have been present as a traditional construction material since the Mesopotamian, Egyptian
318 and Roman periods, its manufacturing process remained almost identical [44]. As for other ceramic
319 products, its process may be divided into three main stages: i) powder processing, ii) shaping and iii) firing
320 [45]. The latter represents the most energy-intensive stage during its manufacturing, because of the heat
321 requirement in the kiln [46]. Despite the fact that the transition towards less CO₂ intensive fuels, such as
322 natural gas [47] or hydrogen[48], this step still remains critical, as shown by Almeida [49]. A literature
323 review carried out by Huarachi Ramos [50] showed that regardless of the country of production, the main
324 stages still remain.

325 First, the raw materials, which are most commonly different types of clays, are excavated from open pits.
326 For this, the use of hydraulic excavators and transportation trucks were considered in this study. In general,
327 excavation sites are located close to the manufacturing plant and, therefore, the transport distance can
328 be minimised [51]. Once the clay is extracted, it is sized down in different steps until the desired
329 granulometry is achieved. The use of a rotary crusher with rated power of 112 kW and an 80-tonnes
330 production rate was simulated to break down the large lumps of clay. Then, through the secondary
331 crushing process the clay grain size is further reduced to below 15 mm. For this, a regular pan mill was
332 selected. The clay is then mixed with water to obtain a homogenized mass with a predefined plasticity.
333 The amount of water used is related to the forming method, ranging from hand-made moulding, semi-dry
334 pressing, to soft mud extrusion, etc. In this study, the latter was considered for the LCI. For this, a total
335 content of 11% of water is added to the mix. The extruder delivers a clay column that is then subjected to
336 the cutting process to form the bricks. Following, the drying process takes place at a temperature that

usually range between 75-90 °C, where the excess heat from the kiln is used [51]. After drying, the bricks usually contain less than 3% of water and are subjected to the firing process at a temperature between 800-1000 °C [49], [51]–[53]. A tunnel kiln was adopted as the most representative technology for Europe [54]. For the processes described in **Figure 3** (Clay Brick), different sources of LCI were used in order to quantify the mean input values and the standard deviation used in every stage as shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Literature review on the Life Cycle Inventory for the production of 1 kg of finished Clay Brick

Clay Bricks Author (year)	Loc. Code	Inputs for the production of 1 kg of finished Brick				Share of Primary Energy			Ref.
		Clay [kg]	Water [kg]	Sand [kg]	Energy [kWh]	Electricity	Diesel	Fuel	
German National Association of Brick Industries (1998)	DE	1.17	0.19	0.20 ^{*1}	0.62	9.0%	5.0%	86.0%	[52]
Ecoinvent 3.8 - "clay brick production, GLO" (2002)	GLO	1.35	0.03	0.01	0.52	8.0%	2.0%	90.0%	[55]
Koroneos (2007)	GR	1.21	0.16	0.00	0.58	2.5%	11.5%	86.0%	[46]
Almeida (2010)	PT	1.22	0.10	0.00	0.35	10.0%	2.0%	88.0%	[49]
Gomes (2012)	BR	1.30	0.003	0.00	1.39 ^{*2}	0.2%	0.1%	100%	[51]
Kua Wei H. & Kamath S. (2014)	SG	1.11	0.13	0.00	0.91	17.0%	0.0%	83.0%	[56]
Giama & Papadopoulos (2015)	GR	0.96	0.08	0.00	0.41	No information			[57]
Souza et al. (2016)	BR	1.59	0.13	0.00	0.91	4.0%	5.0%	91.0%	[10]
Muñoz (2018)	ES	1.25	0.19	0.00	1.07	No information			[11]
^{*1} Value out of date. ^{*2} Not considered for the average because the technology is not representative for Europe	Avg.	1.24	0.11	0.00	0.67	8.4%	4.3%	87.3%	
	Std.	0.16	0.06	0.00	0.26	0.05	0.04	0.03	

2.4.4 Dry-Mix Mortar, Plasters and Renders Manufacturing

In this study 4 different types of mixes were used for the analysis. A pure hydrated lime mortar mix was considered for the plaster layer, while a cement-based mortar mix was used for the render layer as well as for the normal and thin laying mortar composition. Mix proportions, thermal and mechanical properties for each layer are presented in **Table 2**. The inventory information for MRP manufacturing was based on the detailed process-based inventory of Cuenca et al. [58]. An additional step comprising the drying process of natural sand was included, by considering the amount of heat necessary for drying the sand from 5% to 1% water content, equal to 0.06 kWh per kg of dry sand, while using natural gas as fuel. To account for geographical correlation, the electricity mix in the processes was substitute to the corresponding local mix in Germany displayed in Table A1.

2.4.5 Construction & Use Phase

Construction related activities are not covered in the present work, since there are no significant differences between the analysed wall compositions. The transport distances from the manufacturing plants to the construction site were taken as 100 km for both CSB and CB, while 80 km were taken for the MRP and insulation material, based on average distances published in EPDs [59], [60]. The use phase of a building, analogue to the time when living beings age [61], is strictly related to the materials service life and their performance. In fact, a proper definition of the system boundary, representing the goal, scope and definition of the timespan employed in the analysis, will have a direct influence on the final environmental impact [62]. In the present work, it is considered that all included construction materials withstand the studied service life of 50 years, and thus, no activities regarding maintenance is assessed.

363 Regarding the scenarios for simulating each different insulation thicknesses, Equation 5 provides the
 364 emissions for each calculation step. E_i represents each emission or input flow. For each new calculation
 365 step, the additional embodied footprint related to the transport (E_T) and manufacturing (E_W) of the
 366 insulation material as well as the reduction of OE (E_{HVAC}) is considered in the analysis.

$$E_i = E_{i-1} + E_T * \Delta M_{w_i} + E_W * \Delta M_{w_i} + E_{HVAC} * \Delta OE_i \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

367 2.4.6 Operational energy use in reference building

368 The open-source software Energy-Plus [22] was used to quantify the energy requirement profile of each
 369 wall combination. The building model selected for the simulation is the MOD-910, based on ASHRAE
 370 Standard [63]. This choice was made due to its well-documented theoretical design, which allows for a
 371 robust validation. The simulation utilized a typical meteorological year (TMY) from the Climate-
 372 OneBuilding database, representing the climatic conditions of Frankfurt [64]. Specific properties for the
 373 roof and floor construction systems are outlined in **Table 5**, while supplementary material provides
 374 additional details on windows glazing and the building characteristics. It should be noted that no
 375 distinction was made between thin joint mortar and normal mortar configurations, and the thermal
 376 coefficient of the brick was considered representative. Furthermore, this study did not explicitly model
 377 user behaviour, but set heating and cooling limit temperatures at 20 °C and 28 °C, respectively. Different
 378 insulation thicknesses were modelled as discrete scenarios and then interpolated via *cubic spline* in
 379 Matlab. The simulation results are shown in **Figure 4**, where the yearly OE requirement for each wall profile
 380 in relation with the insulation thickness is displayed, while normalized to the building's surface and HVAC
 381 efficiency. In this study, the seasonal coefficient of performance (SCOP) is set to 3, based on the technology
 382 average efficiency values reported by the STRATEGO project [65].

383
 384 **Figure 4:** Yearly Operational Energy requirement as a function of the insulation thickness

385
 386 **Table 5:** Roof and floor properties considered in the MOD-910 simulation

Element	λ [W/m/K]	Thickness [m]	U [W/m²/K]	R [m².K/W]	Density [kg/m³]	C_p [J/kg/K]
Roof						
Internal Plaster	0.51	0.01	51.00	0.020	1700	960
Plasterboard	0.16	0.01	16.00	0.063	950	840
Fiberglass Quilt	0.04	0.3	0.358	2.794	12	840
Roof Deck	0.14	0.019	7.386	0.136	530	900

Floor							
Insulation	0.04	1.007	0.040	25.175			
Concrete slab	1.13	0.08	14.125	0.071	1400	1000	

387 2.5 Sensitivity analysis & scenario descriptions

388 2.5.1 Sensitivity of indicators

389 One of the main benefits of the proposed methodology are the various possibilities to interpret the results
 390 and parametric studies that can be conducted. The fact that an LCA methodology is inherent deterministic
 391 where uncertainties are included in the input parameters and assumptions made, it is vital to understand
 392 up to what extent the results are reliable, and up to which degree they are modify with changes in the
 393 input parameters. For this, two approaches are followed. Firstly, the sensitivity of each mid-point and end-
 394 point indicator as a function of the insulation thickness was studied. All different indicators were
 395 normalized to their minimal value in order to be able to compare them in a single matrix. This type of
 396 analysis delivers valuable insights in the building's environmental behaviour and should be included in any
 397 design process. Secondly, the influence of the main parameters dominating the results were studied.
 398 These were the electricity mix used for the building's OE requirement, the SCOP considered for the HVAC
 399 system and the potential carbon sequestration of the lime-based materials.

400 2.5.2 Forecasted electricity mix & SCOP

401 As considered in the FU, the analysis represents the operation of a reference building for 50 years. This
 402 means that the energy provided to satisfy the OE requirement will be in accordance with Germany's
 403 electricity mix development. Looking at the country's decarbonization pathway and recent energy polices
 404 [66], GHG neutrality will be achieved by 2045 [67]. In this study, this milestone was selected for the
 405 simulation. The corresponding distribution of the electricity mix and background data used is provided in
 406 Table A1. The SCOP of HVAC's has a direct influence in the building's OE requirement. As stated by the
 407 IRENA agency [9], one of the main strategies of Europe is to achieve climate neutrality with emphasis on
 408 the energy efficiency of buildings. For this reason, in this case study also the effect of an increasing SCOP
 409 is considered.

410 2.5.3 Lime carbonation

411

412

413

Figure 5: The Lime Cycle composed of three main reactions

414 The lime cycle, represented in **Figure 5**, theoretically allows for an infinite loop of limestone usage,
 415 resulting in net zero CO_2 emissions after a full cycle. In practice, the production of 1 tonne of lime generates

416 approximately 1.2 tonnes of CO_{2e} emissions, which is nearly 1.53 times the process related emissions (786
 417 kg CO_{2e} per ton CaO) and is due to the use of fossil fuels during the kiln operation and electricity generation
 418 [4]. A recent report published by EuLA, address different projects that examine the quantification of the
 419 carbonation potential of lime in different fields of applications [68]. Furthermore, an extensive literature
 420 review on natural and enhanced carbonation of lime has been carried out by Grosso et. al upon request
 421 of EuLA [69], [70]. According to this research, a carbonation rate between 80-92% and even 20-23% after
 422 100 years, with affected material depths less than 191 mm can be expected for pure air lime mortars and
 423 mixed air lime mortars respectively. Moreover, while the carbonation potential of these materials is well
 424 studied, the one regarding calcium silicate bricks is less conclusive. In the latest roadmap published by the
 425 German CSB Association [39], based on 20 observations of CSB from 1903 onwards, a carbonation rate of
 426 90% can still be expected after 50 years of service life [71]. These results were further confirmed by [72].
 427 Therefore, these values are also applied in the present simulation for evaluating the impact of the
 428 maximum disclosed carbonation potential of lime on the building's carbon footprint. For the case of MRP,
 429 Equation 6 introduced by Grosso et. al [69], this was employed to estimate the carbonation potential after
 430 50 years (CR₅₀). Based on the carbonation reaction of **Figure 5**, around 0.59 kg of CO₂ will be absorbed for
 431 each kg of portlandite to form calcium carbonate. Here, **MCR** represents the maximum natural
 432 carbonation rate, **K** is the carbonation constant and **t** the time in days.

$$CR(\%) = \frac{MCR * K * \sqrt{t}}{depth} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

433

434

Table 6: Maximal carbonation of lime-based construction materials

Material	MCR	K [mm/√day]	CR ₅₀	Ca(OH) ₂ content [kg/FU]	Max CO ₂ - uptake [kg/FU]
Render	0.92	0.25	0.15	9.12	0.84
Plaster	0.92	1.00	0.62	12.16	4.49
CSB	-	-	0.90	42.55	22.77

435 **3 Results & Discussion**

436 **3.1 Life Cycle Inventory**

437 This section provides a detailed and transparent overview of the LCI developed for the present study. It
 438 summarizes each step during manufacturing of CSB and CB, following the procedure described above.
 439 Regarding the electricity mix, table A.1 (supplementary material) shows the relative amount of each
 440 energy source along with the background processes used to model its production. From this, **Table 7** shows
 441 the LCI for the production of CSBs and **Table 8** for CBs manufacturing.

442

Table 7: LCI - Calcium Silicate Brick manufacturing

CSB Manufacturing		Processed Amount		Inventory Amount		Source & Notes
Process	Amount	Unit	Amount	Unit		
Storage & Mixing						
Input	Sand	9.10E-01	kg	9.10E+02	kg / t CSB	Resource, in ground
	Sand quarrying	1.13E-02	MJ	1.15E+01	MJ / t CSB	Ecoinvent - "diesel burned in building machine, APOS S, GLO"
	Sand Transport by conveyor belt	3.64E-06	kWh	4.00E-03	kWh / t sand	Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed
	Lime	7.00E-02	kg	7.00E+01	kg / t CSB	Lime manufacturing - SUBLime
	Lime Transport	6.65E-03	t.km	9.50E+01	km	Ecoinvent - "transport freight lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, APOS S, RoW"
	Mixer operation	3.92E-03	kWh	4.00E+00	kWh / t CSB	Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed
Output	CSB - Dry Mix	9.80E-01	kg			
Reaction Vessel						
Input	CSB - Dry Mix	9.80E-01	kg			
	Water	2.25E-02	kg	3.22E-01	kg/kg lime	Ecoinvent - "tap water production, conventional treatment, APOS S, Europe without Switzerland"
Output	CSB - Wet Mix	1.00E+00	kg			
Pressing						
Input	CSB - Wet Mix	1.00E+00	kg			
	Press operation	7.12E-03	kWh	7.10E+00	kWh / t CSB	Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed
Output	CSB - Raw	1.00E+00	kg			
Autoclaving						
Input	CSB - Raw	1.00E+00	kg			
	Fresh water in steam	2.03E-01	kg	2.02E+02	kg / t CSB	Ecoinvent - "tap water production, conventional treatment, APOS S, Europe without Switzerland"
	Fuel Steam generation	3.24E-01	MJ	3.24E+02	MJ / t CSB	Natural Gas: 95% Ecoinvent – "Heat and power co generation, natural gas 1MW electrical lean burn, APOS S, Europe without Switzerland"
	Fuel Steam generation	1.71E-02	MJ	1.70E+01	MJ / t CSB	Light Fuel Oil: 5% Ecoinvent – "heat production heavy fuel oil at industrial furnace, 1MW, APOS S, Europe without Switzerland"
Output	CSB	1.00E+00	kg			

Table 8: LCI - Clay Brick manufacturing

CB Manufacturing		Processed Amount		Inventory Amount		Source & Notes
Process	Amount	Unit	Amount	Unit		
Clay Quarry						
Input						
	Clay	1.24E+00	kg	1.24E+00	t / t brick	<i>Resource, in ground</i>
	Clay quarrying hydraulic excavators and dump trucks considered	1.04E-01	MJ	8.36E+01	MJ / t clay	<i>Ecoinvent - "diesel burned in building machine, APOS S, GLO"</i>
Output	Clay extracted	1.24E+00	kg			
Milling						
Input	Clay extracted	1.24E+00	kg			
	Prim. Crushing Rotary Crusher	1.74E-03	kWh	1.40E+00	kWh / t clay	<i>Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed</i>
	Water	1.24E-02	kg	1.00E+01	kg / t clay	<i>Ecoinvent - "tap water production, conventional treatment, APOS S"</i>
	Sec. Crushing Pan Mill	4.46E-03	kWh	3.60E+00	kWh / t clay	<i>Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed</i>
Output	Clay sized	1.25E+00	kg	1.23E+01		
Forming						
Input	Clay sized	1.25E+00	kg			
	Water	1.36E-01	kg	1.10E+02	kg / t clay	<i>Ecoinvent - "tap water production, conventional treatment, APOS S"</i>
	Forming Extruder with mixer	3.01E-02	kWh	2.40E+01	kWh / t clay mix	<i>Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed</i>
	Cutting	1.63E-03	kWh	1.30E+00	kWh / t clay mix	<i>Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed</i>
Output	Green brick	1.39E+00	kg			
Drying & Firing						
Input	Green brick	1.39E+00	kg			
	Tunnel Kiln Heat	2.11E+00	MJ	2.11E+03	MJ / t brick	<i>Ecoinvent - "Heat production natural gas at industrial furnace 100kW, APOS_S, Europe without Switzerland"</i>
	Tunnel Kiln Operation	2.01E-02	kWh	2.01E+01	kWh / t brick	<i>Electricity Mix - SUBLime designed</i>
Output	Clay Brick	1.00E+00	kg			
	Water	1.49E-01	kg	1.20E+02	kg / t clay	<i>Emission to air</i>

446 3.2 Life Cycle Impact assessment

447 This section presents the life cycle impact assessment findings of the analysed wall compositions. For each
 448 wall type, the results are displayed as a function of the insulation thickness. The abbreviations used for
 449 each impact category are referenced in **Table 1**. The wall compositions with the best performance, using
 450 CSB and CB, were selected for the sensitivity analysis regarding the electricity mix composition, the SCOP
 451 efficiency, and the effective CO₂ sequestration by carbonation as discussed in previous sections.

452 **Figure 6** and **Figure 7** display all the mid-point and end-point impact scores of each analysed combination,
 453 while compared with the insulation thickness, respectively. Although the interpretation may seem
 454 challenging, some general information can be easily extracted. For instance, it can be seen that those

455 impact categories that show considerable differences in the impact score for small insulation thicknesses
456 are rather controlled by the OE requirement, because the insulation property of the CSB and the CB differ
457 considerably. In fact, CSB-wall compositions require 3 times more energy when using insulation
458 thicknesses between 0 and 5 cm. On the contrary, impact categories that show similar values for low
459 amounts of insulation are rather MEF-controlled and are very sensitive to the addition of mineral wool. It
460 is also possible to see that there is a dependency between the MEF and the OE requirement of the building
461 for each analysed environmental impact. Moreover, the optimal thickness insulation is lower for clay bricks
462 than for calcium-silicate bricks because of their lower thermal conductivity. The wall combinations that
463 employ thin layer mortar (represented by dashed lines) consistently produce environmentally friendlier
464 results compared to the same wall systems with normal joint mortar. Despite having a higher cement
465 content in the thin layer mortar mix, the lower material requirements in the functional unit (see **Table 3**)
466 leads to better environmental outcomes. Furthermore, the structural performance of thin layer mortars
467 is higher when considering the characteristic compressive strength of masonry, which makes the
468 equivalent thickness lower and is thus lowering the amount of material needed to satisfy the same FU.

469 It is observed that in some impact categories such as TAP, ODP, NRE and IR, a better environmental
470 performance can be reached with CSB even with a higher amount of insulation placed. However, on the
471 contrary, when considering CP, LO, ME and POCP, clay bricks perform better when employed in their
472 optimum combination. When looking at AAP, AETP, AEP, GWP, NCP, RI and TETP, similar behaviour can be
473 reached for both type of bricks when selecting the appropriate insulation thickness. To explain this
474 behaviour, a connection between mid-point and end-point scores is reported.

475 **3.2.1 Human health (HH) – related impacts**

476 The HH end-point score is a linear combination of CP, IR, NCP, ODP, RI and POCP and is represented in
477 terms of DALY (Disability-Adjusted Life Years), which is calculated by the mortality and morbidity that
478 characterizes the disease severity [26]. From the aforementioned mid-point indicators, HH is heavily
479 controlled by the human toxicity indicators, namely NCP and CP (around 80% and 6% of the impact score,
480 respectively) and the particle matter formation, RI (around 10%). It can be seen that the dominant process
481 governing NCP and thus the HH indicator is the OE requirement, followed by the mineral wool
482 manufacturing process. Therefore, the interaction between OE consumption and insulation happens at
483 low values of the insulation thickness, while the absolute value of the indicator reaches a better
484 performance for the CB wall composition. When looking at the NCP of the CSB and CB, similar values can
485 be found, namely 0,09 and 0,10 kg C₂H₃Cleq. Interestingly, the main chemical substance controlling this
486 indicator is the arsenic ion emitted to the surface water during electricity production, especially in the case
487 of biofuel and hard coal usage. On the contrary, when looking at the CP, the main affecting process is the
488 combustion of natural gas emitting aromatic hydrocarbons in the air. For this reason, the partial
489 contribution of CB is around 1.7 times as much as those related to CSB (0.19 kg C₂H₃Cleq vs 0.11 kg
490 C₂H₃Cleq). Again, the contribution of lime production inside CSB manufacturing is considerable. Regarding
491 the particulate matter formation, represented by the IR indicator, the electricity production which uses
492 25% of hard coal as fuel is predominantly responsible of the generation of fine particulates. Moreover, the
493 quarrying operation for sand obtention in both the CSB and CB manufacturing process releases high
494 amounts of nitrogen oxides which also contributes to this indicator.

495 **3.2.2 Ecosystems quality (EQ) – related impacts**

496 With the EQ indicator, the LCA analysis aims to understand the potential damage to biodiversity loss. By
497 looking at the results along with the conversion factors from **Table 1**, it can be seen that the governing
498 mid-point category is LO, which is responsible for 90% of this impact. This indicator is heavily controlled
499 by the electricity production, in particular the biofuel process. For this reason, the LO impact score shows
500 a decreasing tendency with increasing insulation thickness. This behaviour is further extrapolated to the
501 end-point indicator.

502 **3.2.3 Resource availability (RA) – related impacts**

503 The RA or requirement is an unweighted combination of the NRE and ME requirement. When looking at
504 the mid-point values in **Figure 6** it becomes clear that the end-point impact category is controlled by the
505 NRE. This impact category accounts for the extracted total non-renewable primary energy. As can be seen,
506 this indicator is heavily depending on the OE requirement, since around 43% of the electricity used in the
507 building comes from non-renewable sources such as hard coal and/or natural gas. Nevertheless, there is
508 a substantial contribution related to the material production, which can be observed when looking at the
509 minimum score of each combination. In fact, the NRE requirement for CSB production to fulfil the system's
510 FU is around 294 MJ, while the corresponding for CB is almost 500 MJ. This difference can be explained by
511 comparing the two manufacturing processes. As it is shown in the LCI, the amount of energy requirement
512 during autoclaving CSB is around 6,18 times less than the amount needed for firing CB. Moreover, the
513 biggest contribution to the CSB NRE-footprint is related to the lime production rather than to the bricks
514 themselves, which requires almost half of the energy (140 MJ) for operating the lime kiln. The natural gas
515 alone needed for the CB firing process makes up 317 MJ, while the rest comes from the electricity
516 production (129 MJ) and diesel combustion during the quarrying of clays (47 MJ).

517 **3.2.4 Climate Change (CC)**

518 The CC endpoint category displays the same result as the mid-point indicator GWP. As a reference, 1000
519 kWh of OE electricity consumption, which corresponds to 20 kWh per m² per year times 50 years of service
520 life, produces around 407 kg of CO_{2e} emissions. More than 90% of these emissions are generated by the
521 hard coal (259 kg CO_{2e}) and natural gas (113 kg CO_{2e}) combustion. This highlights the significance of the OE
522 requirement as a driver to reduce the building's stock carbon footprint. When looking at the CSB and CB
523 manufacturing process, it can be observed that the energy requirement of CB production is much higher
524 than the one of CSB. This is because of the higher temperature needed during the firing process, where
525 roughly 17.8 kg CO_{2e} are emitted to produce 340.9 kg of CB, represented by the CB-1.2_T wall combinations
526 (**Figure 7**). Moreover, the production of 460 kg of CSB in the case of the CSB-2.0_T, releases almost 42.5 kg
527 of CO_{2e} emissions, from which the manufacturing of lime is responsible for almost 35.0 kg, which is more
528 than 80% of the GHG emissions of the CSB manufacturing process. From this, each cm of mineral wool
529 added to the wall cross section adds around 1.2 kg CO_{2e}. For this reason, the threshold between OE and
530 MEF tends to higher insulation thickness, especially for the CSB wall combinations.

Figure 6: Mid-point impact scores for the reference wall combinations per FU

531

532

533

534

535

Figure 7: End-point areas of damage for the reference wall combinations per FU

536 **3.2.5 Single score point**

537 The single score point, displayed in **Figure 8**, facilitates the comparison across different impact categories.
 538 In fact, it represents the tendency previously mentioned, without providing specific details on the different
 539 impact indicators. It summarizes the results of the assessment into one single numerical value, related to
 540 the total impact of a certain category divided by the European population [26]. Both the CSB-2.0_T and CB-
 541 1.2_T wall compositions present the best environmental performance, here represented by the lowest
 542 number of points, and will, therefore, be considered for a detailed analysis.

543

544

Figure 8: Single score for the reference wall combinations per FU

545

546 **3.3 Sensitivity analysis & scenarios results**

547 **Figure 9** shows the variation of each mid-point indicator for the two selected walls as function of the
 548 insulation thickness (CSB-2.0_T and CB-1.2_T). For both cases it can be observed that a first group of impact
 549 categories such as LO, IR, AETP, AEP, GWP, ODP and NRE are OE-controlled, meaning that they benefit
 550 from an increase in the insulation thickness and a consequential lower OE requirement. In fact, even if the
 551 insulation thickness reduces beyond the optimal solution, the expected increase in the impact score is
 552 below 1.03 times the optimum one. As discussed before, these indicators are heavily related to the non-
 553 renewable electricity consumption and therefore represent such behaviour. A second group of impact
 554 categories like AAP, NCP, RI, TAP, TETP, are in a balanced position, where they benefit from the reduction
 555 of the OE requirement up to a certain threshold where the MEF begins to dominate it. Along with this, in
 556 both directions these indicators can increase between 1.05 to 1.20 times the value of the optimum
 557 solution. A third group are the impact categories ME, CP and POCP that can be highlighted as MEF-
 558 controlled, particularly because of the use of mineral wool as insulation material. These indicators have
 559 optimum solutions values at the lower range of insulation thickness and can increase their absolute value
 560 up to 1.5 to 1.8 times for CSB and CB respectively. The CP is heavily affected by high amounts of aromatic
 561 hydrocarbons, especially benzo(a)pyrene, emitted to the air during the stone wool manufacturing.
 562 Similarly, the emissions of non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC) are strongly responsible for
 563 the rapid increase of the POCP impact score. Regarding the ME category, although aluminium is the most
 564 occurring metal in the manufacturing of mineral wool (0.015 kg per kg of insulation), the use of copper is
 565 as critical because of its over 15 times higher impact conversion factor to the MJ surplus [73]. **Figure 10**
 566 shows the analogue analysis at end-point categories. It can be observed that the EQ, RA and CC indicators
 567 are OE-controlled and therefore any measure taken to reduce the energy requirement of the building will
 568 positively affect these indicators. On the contrary, when looking at HH, the selection of materials plays a
 569 determining role and over-dimensioning the mineral wool thickness can lead to an increase of the damage
 570 to human health of up to a factor 1.18.

571
 572 **Figure 9:** normalized Mid-point impact score for a) CSB-2.0_T and b) CB-1.2_T

a)

b)

Figure 10: Normalized End-point impact scores for a) CSB-2.0 τ and b) CB-1.2 τ

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577 3.3.1 Contribution analysis

578 In terms of interpretation of LCA results, the contribution analysis is a key aspect. It allows to further
 579 understand and explain the relationships between mid-point, end-point and processes considered within
 580 the system boundary. The following sections analyse the contribution analysis related to the different
 581 sensitivity scenarios described before. Results regarding end-point categories are given in **Table 9**.
 582 Additionally, Figures A1 to A4 show the contribution of the mid-point and end-point environmental
 583 impacts on the different components of the walls. It can be seen, that the optimum insulation thickness
 584 for walls made with CSB ranges from 9 to 40 cm, while for CB this ranges from 0 to 29 cm, which is
 585 consistent with the previous results. Choosing any extreme of this range may result in an increase of more
 586 than 125% of the impact in the OE-controlled categories. Secondly, OE usage has a significant contribution
 587 to nearly every impact category, with the production of mineral wool being the second largest contributor,
 588 particularly for mid-point categories of CP, ME and POCP. Lastly, the MEF accounted for 4 to 13% of the
 589 total end-point impact, highlighting the importance of considering both MEF and OPE in a comprehensive
 590 evaluation of the environmental impact of buildings.

591

Table 9: End-point scores for the reference & forecasted scenarios

End-point per FU		CSB-2.0T					CB-1.2T				
HH [DALY]		Total	MEF	OE	M. wool	t_{opt} [cm]	Total	MEF	OE	M. wool	t_{opt} [cm]
Reference	Emix 2020	1.37E-03	1.29E-04	1.06E-03	1.78E-04	17	1.33E-03	1.33E-04	1.13E-03	7.34E-05	7
Scenario 1	Emix 2050	9.22E-04	1.29E-04	6.46E-04	1.47E-04	14	8.59E-04	1.34E-04	6.84E-04	4.19E-05	4
	Reduction	33%	0%	39%	18%	18%	36%	0%	39%	43%	43%
Scenario 2	SCOP 10	5.87E-04	1.29E-04	3.63E-04	9.44E-05	9	5.08E-04	1.34E-04	3.75E-04	0.00E+00	0
	Reduction	57%	0%	66%	47%	47%	62%	0%	67%	100%	100%
EQ [PDF m2 yr]											
Reference	Emix 2020	1.38E+02	3.75E+00	1.30E+02	4.99E+00	40	1.46E+02	5.40E+00	1.35E+02	4.99E+00	40
Scenario 1	Emix 2050	4.85E+01	3.76E+00	4.10E+01	3.75E+00	30	5.12E+01	5.41E+00	4.33E+01	2.49E+00	20
	Reduction	65%	0%	68%	25%	25%	65%	0%	68%	50%	50%
Scenario 2	SCOP 10	4.73E+01	3.76E+00	3.99E+01	3.62E+00	29	5.00E+01	5.41E+00	4.21E+01	2.49E+00	20
	Reduction	66%	0%	69%	27%	28%	66%	0%	69%	50%	50%
RA [MJ]											
Reference	Emix 2020	7.39E+03	5.24E+02	6.35E+03	5.18E+02	34	7.82E+03	7.37E+02	6.70E+03	3.80E+02	25
Scenario 1	Emix 2050	1.20E+03	5.26E+02	5.34E+02	1.37E+02	9	1.29E+03	7.38E+02	5.50E+02	0.00E+00	0
	Reduction	84%	0%	92%	74%	74%	84%	0%	92%	100%	100%
Scenario 2	SCOP 10	2.84E+03	5.26E+02	2.03E+03	2.89E+02	19	3.02E+03	7.38E+02	2.15E+03	1.37E+02	9
	Reduction	62%	0%	68%	44%	44%	61%	0%	68%	64%	64%
CC [kg CO_{2e}]											
Reference	Emix 2020	4.89E+02	7.58E+01	3.78E+02	3.53E+01	29	4.84E+02	6.13E+01	3.99E+02	2.43E+01	20
Scenario 1	Emix 2050	1.26E+02	7.60E+01	3.91E+01	1.10E+01	9	1.02E+02	6.14E+01	4.03E+01	0.00E+00	0
	Reduction	74%	0%	90%	69%	69%	79%	0%	90%	100%	100%
Scenario 2	SCOP 10	2.18E+02	7.59E+01	1.22E+02	1.95E+01	16	1.98E+02	6.14E+01	1.28E+02	8.52E+00	7
	Reduction	55%	0%	68%	45%	45%	59%	0%	68%	65%	65%
Scenario 3	S1 + S2 + carbonation	6.80E+01	4.79E+01	1.41E+01	6.09E+00	5	6.57E+01	5.61E+01	1.21E+01	0.00E+00	0
	Reduction	86%	37%	96%	83%	83%	86%	9%	97%	100%	100%

594 3.3.2 Electricity mix forecasting & SCOP efficiency

595 **Figure 11** and **Figure 12** show the relative contribution of the OE use, embodied material, and insulation
596 manufacturing to the four endpoint categories in the forecasted electricity mix scenario. As can be
597 observed, there is a general trend in all categories for less insulation thicknesses as the optimum solution.
598 Moreover, **Table 9** shows the absolute amount of each indicator along with the reduction percentage of
599 the different scenarios, when compared with the reference case. It can be observed that increasing the

600 SCOP (scenario 2) leads to better results in terms of HH and EQ while decarbonising the electricity mix
 601 (scenario 1) affects RA and CC in both types of walls. This is explained by a reduction of the optimum
 602 insulation thickness for each scenario.

603 Regarding scenario 1, the direct impact of OE decreases between 39% to 92% depending on the analysed
 604 damage area. This has two different effects: Firstly, it helps to reduce the final environmental performance
 605 directly between 33% (HH) and 84% (EQ). Secondly, it promotes the reduction of the threshold between
 606 MEF and OE, inducing a decrease in the amount of insulation required and therefore further reducing its
 607 environmental impact. Particularly for the RA and CC impact categories, the role of the MEF in scenario 1
 608 represents the largest contribution. This can be explained by the fact that by decreasing the amount of
 609 fossil fuels used to deliver the OE requirement, both the CO_{2e} footprint and the NRE use decreases more
 610 than 90%. It should be mentioned that although the considered mix relies only on renewable energy
 611 sources, neither the GWP nor the NRE is zero. For instance, the production of electricity by solar energy
 612 requires natural gas to operate the plant, which will directly affect both indicators.

613

614

Figure 11: Normalized end-point impact scores & contribution analysis per FU for CSB-2.0_τ & 2050 forecasted electricity mix

615
616 **Figure 12:** Normalized end-point impact scores & contribution analysis per FU for CB-1.2_T & 2050 forecasted electricity mix

617 Moreover, it turned out that the MEF environmental performance without the insulation remain the same
618 in absolute terms although its relative share of the final environmental impact increased for all cases. This
619 highlights the role that construction material manufacturing will play in the coming decades. In fact, when
620 looking at **Figure 12** the optimum insulation thickness for RA and CC is zero. This means, that the mineral
621 wool production plays a decisive role in the building design. Such findings can justify the need to consider
622 bio-based or mineral insulation materials.

623 Regarding scenario 2, the increase in HVAC efficiency has positive effects on all end-point impact
624 categories, especially in the ones that are more affected by mineral wool production. The reduction
625 potentials range between 57% and 66% for HH and EQ respectively. The latter corresponds to a reduction
626 in the insulation thickness from 40 cm to 29 cm and 20 cm for CSB and CB respectively, with an added drop
627 of the OE relative contribution. It can be seen that, although the main driver behind the use of renewable
628 energy sources for the electricity production is the decarbonization of the German industry, this also leads
629 to other benefits which include the reduction of potential damage to human health and ecosystems.

630 **3.3.3 Carbonation**

631 The contribution of the carbonation potential is analysed for the GWP mid-point indicator, since CO₂
632 emissions to the air are not considered in other impact categories. Two scenarios are shown in **Figure 13**
633 and **Figure 14**. First, the reference scenario with the current electricity mix and a SCOP of 3 is analysed.
634 Then, the addition of scenario 1 and 2 are modelled and introduce scenario 3, which is shown in **Table 9**.
635 It can be appreciated, that the carbonation of the render and plaster layers contribute to 1% of the FU
636 carbon footprint. For the case of CSB-2.0_T wall, this value increases up to 5% with the additional
637 carbonation of CSB.

638 If a fully renewable electricity mix is considered and the HVAC system's efficiency is increased to 10
 639 (scenario 3), the relative contribution of the carbonation potential increases. It can be seen, that the
 640 absolute GWP impact decreases from 489 to 68 kg CO_{2e} per m². In this context, the relative contribution
 641 of CSB carbonation plays a major role, namely more than 20% of the total impact. Additionally, the CO_{2e}
 642 uptake of the render and plaster is approximately 7% of the total emissions. These results suggest, that
 643 even if the maximum potential carbonation of lime-based materials is considered, the CO₂ uptake suffers
 644 from an attenuation effect when analysed at a building scale in the current scenario. Firstly, because the
 645 amount of material used is much lower than the structural and insulation ones and secondly because the
 646 role of the MEF in general is dominated by the OE requirement footprint. Furthermore, since a large share
 647 of the GHG emissions linked to lime manufacturing is produced by the combustion of fossil fuels in the
 648 kiln, there is a remaining amount of CO₂ that will not be re-captured. This finding highlights the importance
 649 of developing low-carbon content fuels and carbon capture strategies in the lime manufacturing industry.
 650 Finally, results also highlight the significance of the potential role that carbonation of CSB can play in the
 651 future. For this reason, more research is needed to comprehend and quantify the carbonation potential
 652 of these materials.

653

654 **Figure 13:** GWP per FU for CSB-2.0τ with CO₂ uptake: a) Emix-2020, SCOP = 3.0 b) Emix-2050, SCOP = 10

655

656 **Figure 14:** GWP per FU for CB-1.2_T with CO₂ uptake: a) Emix-2020, SCOP = 3.0 b) Emix-2050, SCOP = 10

657 **4** Limitations

658 It should be noted that the presented results have certain modelling limitations. Firstly, some building's
659 elements were excluded from the LCA analysis as specified in the system boundary definition (**Figure 3**).
660 Secondly, the carbonation potential of CSBs was based on the maximum reported values found in
661 literature and did not explicitly consider the presence of render layer on top of the bricks, potentially
662 leading to lower carbonation values. Lastly, this paper deliberately omitted end-of-life scenarios, as its
663 main focus was to model the interaction between process-based manufacturing and use-stage
664 performance of building materials. However, exploring end-of-life scenarios remains a potential avenue
665 for future research.

666 **5** Conclusions

667 From the results of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

668 Coupling methodology

- 669 • By defining the manufacturing process of any construction material and linking it with OE
670 requirement simulation at the building scale, comprehensive insights on the environmental
671 performance can be achieved at an early stage of design.
- 672 • A link between MEF and OE exists, which, in this study, is represented by the insulation thickness,
673 but its definition will depend on the environmental impact category considered. Mid-point impact
674 categories like LO, IR, AETP, AEP, GWP, ODP and NRE are rather controlled by the OE requirement,
675 while ME, CP and POCP by the MEF. Moreover, at end-point and mid-point levels, this study
676 provides valuable insights that cannot be obtained when looking at a SS only.

677 Life Cycle Inventory & impact assessment

- 678 • A process-based LCI was successfully develop for the manufacturing of CSB and CB, providing
679 valuable data that can be employed by different stakeholders to analyse the environmental
680 performance of such materials.
- 681 • Thin-layer mortars outperformed normal joint mortars in every impact category. From the 12
682 different wall compositions, CSB-2.0_T and CB-1.2_T consistently delivered the best results in their
683 respective groups after considering the masonry vertical load capacity with the equivalent
684 thickness method.
- 685 • Looking at end-point areas of damage, CSB-2.0_T performed better in terms of EQ and RA, while
686 CB-1.2_T did so for HH and CC. This is due to energy requirement during the firing of CB which
687 heavily depends on fossil fuels. In addition, the lime manufacturing process is responsible for more
688 than 80% of the GHG emissions of the CSB.

689 Scenario analysis

- 690 • A transition towards renewable-based energy sources for electricity production may significantly
691 contribute to reductions of damage to HH, EQ, RA and CC of 33%, 65%, 84% and 74% respectively.

692 This also leads to a reduction of the amount of insulation material required to achieve the best
693 environmental performance of a building.

694 • The use of more efficient HVAC systems leads to a major relative effect of the MEF in the total
695 environmental impact outcome of the masonry unit, resulting in a drop in optimum insulation
696 thickness.

697 • Lime-based plasters and renders have a limited capacity to reduce CO₂ emissions by carbonation,
698 with only around 1% reduction at the building scale in the reference scenario. However, if the
699 carbonation potential of CSB would be fully realized, it can have a significant impact on the GWP
700 indicator, leading to a 5% reduction in GHG emissions in the reference scenario. This effect can be
701 further enhanced by combining it with a high HVAC efficiency (with a SCOP of 10) and 100%
702 renewable-based sources for the building's OE, resulting in a total reduction of 86%.

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708 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

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710 discussion, Writing – original draft, paper preparation, Writing – review & editing, results and discussion.
711 Agustin Laveglia: Review & editing, results and discussion. Neven Ukrainczyk: Resources, Writing – review
712 & editing, results and discussion and Supervision. Eddie Koenders: Resources, Writing – review & editing,
713 results and discussion, Supervision.

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